

ARTISTIC FEATURES OF STEPHEN CRANE'S PROSE

Abstract.

The article examines factors predisposing to gradual alienation from the spiritual and moral priorities of the individual in the works of Stephen Crane. The danger of spiritual degradation of the individual, as a process invisible to the person himself, was highlighted by the writer in many works. The superiority of the author's view lies not only in the formulation of the problem of "man and society", but also in the innovative understanding of those traditional factors that takes a person to indifference, depersonalization, contribute to his moral, psychological and even physical degradation, and prevent the "awakening" of his conscience and find the way out of the problems suffocating his mind, his feelings and eager to live. Stephen Crane in his works was deeply aware of the storehouses of the spiritual life of his heroes in close connection with the resolution of the most important issues of life, ridicules lack of culture, ignorance, depletion of the inner spiritual world of man, stupidity, vulgarity, spiritual degradation, arrogance, careerism, feels sympathy with people possessing pessimistic view, those who lost the ability to love, sincerely feel, experience, etc.

Key words: Stephen Crane, prose, alienation, degradation, stream of consciousness

Introduction. Stephen Crane (1871-1900), an outstanding American prose writer and poet, left a bright and original mark on the history of literature. In a short period of creativity, he managed to become the author of numerous works of different genres, successfully working in the field of prose, poetry, and journalism. His collected works were published in six volumes by W. Follett in 1925-26, in the New York publishing house "Knopf" under the general title "The Work of Stephen Crane". Each of the mentioned editions contained two volumes, but this edition was not complete. Having become famous as the creator of the novel "The Red Badge of Courage" which laid the foundations of US military prose, Stephen Crane wrote about one hundred and fifty short stories, most of which have stood the test of time.

Currently, the attention of scientists, writers and people far from science and art is increasingly turning to the works of the end of the past and the beginning of the present century. Completing a round of history, on the eve of the new millennium, man is looking for answers to questions that concern him today in the past, trying to identify and understand the similarities and differences of the changes taking place at the turn of the century. American literature at the turn of the 19th and 20th centuries gave rise to a number of brilliant names, whose work determined many directions in the development of the literary process of our days. One of these writers was the outstanding novelist, short story writer, poet and publicist Stephen Crane.

A brilliant stylist, Crane had a significant influence on subsequent generations of poets, novelists and short story writers in the United States and other countries of the world. Among those who experienced this influence are American, English, Russian authors: E. Hemingway, R. Frost, F. S. Fitzgerald, J. Joyce, W. Wolfe, S. Dovlatov and others.

Stephen Crane's poetry and short stories are of interest to both a wide range of readers and literary scholars. Twice "returned" since the death of the writer, today his work, according to general belief, is included in

the golden fund of American literature. In the modern United States, S. Crane is considered a national classic. His short stories and poetry are included in all anthologies and anthologies, as well as in the compulsory educational program on literature for schools.

The life and creative path of S. Crane coincided with a turning point in the economic and socio-political life of the United States. The 80s-90s of the 19th century were the time when the United States, rapidly developing, "became the largest industrial-agrarian power in the world" [1]. The first monopolists and oligarchs are celebrated as folk heroes; on the other hand, there is a massive impoverishment of society.

Changes in the economy could not but affect the spiritual sphere. The thoughts of the average American boil down to the desire to make a fortune at any cost. An era is coming when getting rich is considered a goal and a calling in life. The establishment of a period of mercantilism and triumphant pragmatism gives rise to anti-artism as a characteristic feature of a certain part of US literature of that time [1; p.514]. The "Gilded Age" inherits the previous era of Romanticism, witnessing its degeneration into a "genteel tradition". They are fought by adherents of new forms of artistic thinking, to which Crane joins. The most consonant with the author's ideas about the method of abandoning outdated, in his opinion, romantic norms in literature turns out to be "veritism," the creator and theorist of which was H. Garland [2]. He sees the artist's new role as a truthful description of all aspects of reality based on the author's life experience. In an effort to achieve this goal, S. Crane in his works combines artistic techniques characteristic of romanticism with realistic ones, impressionistic ones with naturalistic ones, etc. Already during his lifetime, S. Crane's fame as an experimenter was established, but because of this, his works caused distrust among most critics and for a long time were not the subject of serious research.

Stephen Crane's creativity in literary criticism

S. Crane lived a short life and began writing at an early age of fourteen. This was greatly facilitated by the

journalism studies of Stephen's mother and brothers and sisters. The writer's literary career began with the publication of the story "Uncle Jake and the Bell Handle" in 1885, a little later the collection "Sullivan County Sketches" and some other works appeared. But fame came to S. Crane only in 1895 after the publication of the novel "The Red Badge of Courage". In a relatively short period (Crane actively wrote for about 15 years), he created a large number of works, mainly in a small genre, but the most successful, without exaggeration, can be considered the short stories written after 1897.

During his lifetime, S. Crane's talent was perceived in different ways: a famous journalist, a well-known writer and poet. After the writer's death in 1900, it was as if he had been completely forgotten. But, starting from 1921, interest in the writer's work and life was renewed. On the 50th anniversary of Crane's birth, a commemorative plaque was placed on the public library building in his hometown of Newark, which currently houses the Stephen Crane Archives. It contains the pedigree and photographs of his family, more than 100 letters, about 200 articles and newspaper clippings.

At the same time (1923), the first biography of Crane appeared, published by Thomas Beer [3]. However, many researchers such as Th. Cross, Gandal, Keith and others accused the author of myth-making dispute the factual accuracy of this book [4;5]. V. Starett spoke more kindly about this work: "Mr. Beer's excellent research is far from a documentary biography" [6].

After World War II, a large number of monographs appeared devoted to various aspects of S. Crane's work. All these studies can be divided into several groups. First of all, literary biographies should be highlighted, where, along with a description of the facts of the writer's personal life, some aspects of his works are considered. As a rule, the authors of these books do not set themselves the goal of making a detailed literary analysis of the works, but turn to the most characteristic and important moments of S. Crane's work. This group includes the works of American and European scientists J. Berryman [7], J. Cazemajou [8], J. Colvert [9], R. Franchere [10], K. Linson [11], B. Knapp [12] which, together with biographical material, examine Stephen Crane's novels and short stories from different points of view. Many of them pay special attention to the late works of the writer. An important place in this group is occupied by a detailed biography of Robert Stallman. Professor Stallman's remarks on religious symbolism, irony and style of Stephen Crane are emphasized in this work [13].

The second group of works is mainly analytical. The first among them is considered to be the fundamental work of Lars Ohnebrink, published in 1950. And although the Swedish scientist's research was devoted to the emergence of naturalism in American literature and examined the work of several authors, he paid a lot of attention to the works of S. Crane. The researcher provides an analysis of Crane's creativity and his "literary credo." In general, the study is comparative in nature, therefore, in the study, Crane is compared with Zola, Turgenyev, Tolstoy and Ibsen, respectively [14]. But it

seems that the naturalistic tendency in Crane's works is unnecessarily exaggerated by the author.

D. Hoffman's book "The Poetry of Stephen Crane" appeared a little later in 1957. In it, the author examines mainly Crane's poems, making interesting comments about the impressionism and symbolism of the writer, and comparing them with the prose of Crane himself, as well as his predecessors (E. Poe, Beers, Hawthorne and others) and his followers, mainly E. Hemingway [15].

A great contribution to the study of Crane's legacy was made by E. Solomon, whose study "From Parody to Realism" contains many interesting ideas about the progressive movement of Crane's work towards realism. However, sometimes his observations are limited due to the fact that they are derived from one single thesis about the parodic nature of all the writers' novels and short stories [16].

Some results in Crane studies in the 60s were summed up by Donald Gibson's book "The Work of Stephen Crane" (1968) [17]. It examines all the main works of the writer. According to Gibson, Crane did not have a clearly defined philosophical concept, but he was sensitive to all the trends of the last decades of the 19th century. Therefore, his analysis is distinguished by an increased emphasis on the naturalism and determinism of S. Crane. According to the critic, "The Open Boat" deserves the highest rating.

The 70-80s were the most fruitful for Crane studies. Literary scholars actively developed the ideas of their predecessors and expressed their own thoughts. In this regard, the work of Milne Holton (1972) [18] is indicative, whose study represents a detailed analysis of most short stories and novels by an experienced critic. Based on the clarification of the differences between a person's understanding of reality and reality as such, the author finds that a distinctive feature of S. Crane's reality is the indifference of nature to the fate of man. Much of Holton's analysis is based on the connection between Crane's fiction and journalistic articles, and this is his undeniable merit. At the same time, Holton, in our opinion, unnecessarily pushes the issue of Crane's connection with absurdist ideas. Similar to this concept is the point of view of M. La'France [19], who makes the connection between the external world and human experience, the world of facts and ethical standards of behavior, the basis of his interpretations of S. Crane's central stories.

Thomas Gullason is actively developing Crane themes; he not only publishes the works of Stephen Crane, but also prefaces them with introductory articles and interesting comments. Gullason highlighted the features of Crane's poetics: impressionistic style, cinematic style of presentation, use of symbolism and tragic perception of reality [20].

F. Bergon made a serious contribution to the study of Crane's legacy, giving a detailed analysis and high appreciation of the writer's style. His small but informative monograph offers rich material for both citation and polemics [21].

A major study, moreover, entirely based on the material of short stories and novellas, was the book by Chester Wolford, published in 1989. The author offers

an overview of almost all of Crane's works in the short story genre. A clear merit of the scientist can be considered the emphasized attention to works of short prose that were ignored before him; in addition, the publication contains a selection of letters and excerpts from critical articles related to Crane's short stories. At the same time, the desire to consider as many works as possible led, in our opinion, to a formal review of individual stories. The basic concept of the study is not always indisputable: "the conflict of chaos and order," expressed in the nihilism and skepticism of the writer [22].

It should be noted that interest in studying the legacy of Stephen Crane continues unabated abroad. Over the past decade, many articles have been published in specialized literary journals; several dissertations on Crane topics have been defended in the USA and Europe. In order to mark the centenary of the publication of "The Red Badge of Courage" in 1995, a number of new publications appeared.

Psychological analysis of S. Crane's "Maggie: A Girl of the Streets".

From the first works in the creativity of naturalist Stephen Crane, main themes emerged are: the life of urban slums; the tragedy of war; children's deprivation; human degradation. The reader can observe all these themes described in a unique work named "Maggie: A Girl of the Streets" (1893) by S. Crane. "Maggie: A Girl of the Streets" is the story of a young worker who is driven to work by the icy indifference of her neighbors. Publishers rejected the book, and Crane published the story at his own expense under the pseudonym Johnston Smith.

There is no development in the character of Maggie; Crane's story was born in a different cultural tradition, and its genre model was not a biographical novel at all, but an edifying story, which was popular in Puritan America - about bad boys who end their lives on the gallows, or girls of bad behavior who die because of their mother. True, the moral meaning in Crane's story is radically changed. The essence of Maggie's tragedy lays not so much in the monstrous influence of the environment, but in the weakness of the individual. The writer wanted to show the poverty experiment. He tried to make it obvious that the root of life was a kind of moral cowardice. The worst thing about Maggie's fate is not that she became a prostitute, but that she has no independence and self-confidence. She has lost confidence in herself - it was this spiritual support that Crane called "courage." Maggie is presented in the story only as an object of violence, seduction and deception; she lived her short life without discovering her own self. The heroine only before her death realizes that those around her see in her only a thing that they want to possess. Maggie can't even do that.

S. Crane's important discovery in his first story was, of course, the style and methods of presenting people, things, and events. The pervasive irony of the narrative immediately attracts attention. "Maggie" is "the first ironic story to come from the pen of an American writer. Crane's irony is very diverse. First of all, it is burlesque, or the ironic-comic incongruity of high sayings in the description of everyday and base objects.

Such epic concepts as "honor", "glory", "battle", "champion", etc., are combined with street slang, and lush rhetorical turns ("cyclone of violence and volcano of vulgarity") stand next to simple and accurate descriptions of the actions and experiences of characters, religious vocabulary used to describe inappropriate objects.

Another type of irony is the discrepancy between real facts and the characters' perceptions. For example, Pete's vulgar and wretched appearance, his rude manners and words are described, and Maggie sees in him a gentleman from decent society, a knight and a hero. Such kind of men embody the heroine's fall down the social ladder, from the splendor of respectable restaurants and theaters into the darkness of unlit and poor neighborhoods, from the noise of the city into the silence of nothingness. This important motif runs throughout the book and reaches its climax in the final scene, when Maggie's mother, a drunkard and brawler, a regular at cheap bars and police stations, "forgives" her errant daughter. S. Crane shows how distorted reality is in the stereotypes of current morality, which are embodied by both philistine gossip and church sermons. Finally, there is a deeply tragic irony in the story, the essence of which lies in the glaring discrepancy between the objective course of events and the aspirations of the heroes.

The climax of the story is Maggie's death. It is given indirectly and also impressionistically. Death itself is not described, but in the last paragraph of the chapter the corresponding words are used twice - in the description of color and sound: "the deadly black color of the river" and "the various sounds of life, which at a distance seemed joyful and inaccessible, were barely heard and died in silence" [23]. Nothing else is said in the text, so the reader remains in the dark about what happened - suicide or violence that ended in murder, as hinted at by the image of the last of the men the heroine met.

It is worth noting the mastery of artistic detail in the final scene. The brother informs his mother of Maggie's death, and she, "with her mouth full," "continues eating" and begins to cry as soon as she finishes her coffee. Here the first detail appears in her words - her daughter's children's shoes; the mother mentions them at least four times, and then picturesquely takes them out of the other room. And these shoes take on a symbolic meaning. The role of another leitmotif of the finale is played by the phrase - the question of the neighbors who have come running: "Will you now forgive your ungrateful, bad daughter?" The sad fate of the heroine looks distorted and stupid in this standard formula - it is strange to ask for forgiveness from a mother who pushed her daughter to death with cruelty and indifference. The tragic irony of these exclamations reaches its limit in the last lines of the story - the mother suffers, but how wildly and absurdly the hackneyed formula sounds in her mouth: "I forgive her! I forgive her!" [23].

Conclusion. An analysis of the stories of the first decade of Crane's creative activity showed that at first the writer followed the tradition of an action-packed short story, but already in that period he paid more and

more attention to the motives of human actions, to the psyche of the “little man.”

Over time, the writer’s interest in the psychological development of the plot leads to the fact that chance, as the basis of the short story genre, although important, plays a sinister, tragic role. Violent death in the lives of heroes becomes not only possible, but sometimes also an inevitable reality. This is largely explained by the author’s worldview and the peculiarities of his contemporary spiritual and socio-economic situation.

The complication of the image of a person occurs due to the gradual displacement of external action in his prose and the transfer of the main emphasis to the depiction of an internal event, closely related to the perception of the surrounding world. While allowing for the life-like self-development of an artistic character, Crane at the same time focuses all his attention on depicting one or more aspects of human psychology.

The author gradually enlarges the features of the “little man,” emphasizing a particular quality in each work. Starting with the depiction of masks - “little man”, “fat man”, “quiet man”, usually gripped by fear or undergoing initiation – S. Crane over time introduces new types - “sage”, “courageous hero”, “business man”.

Conventionality in the portrayal of the hero fades into the background, although it does not completely disappear, because Crane did not set himself the goal of delving into human psychology or creating complex characters. At the same time, depicting the types of hero taken from one perspective - “believer”, “preferring self-deception”, “man of honor”, etc. - the author does not simplify them to the monotony of portraits. He manages to write out the subtle nuances of a person’s experiences.

S. Crane's personal experience undoubtedly enriches everything he wrote. The autobiographical makes its way through individual features and episodes both in short stories and in poetry. We owe the biographical component the appearance of such images as “officer” in short stories and “believer/Christian”, as well as “poet” in lyrics. Some features of the hero in his prose and poetry allow us to conclude that he is endowed with clearly defined national characteristics. In the novel it is self-sufficiency, individualism, selfishness. In the lyrics we can talk about a hero who prescribes standards of behavior for himself and in one way or another opposes tradition.

It seems that in the image of a person emerging in the corpus of prose and verse under study, some features common to the hero of works of both genres can be traced. These, in our opinion, can include naivety, cowardice, arrogance, and complacency. Crane is a wonderful master of irony, which is manifested in the creation of images of the listed characters. The traits of an ideal hero - stoicism, courage, a high understanding of duty and honor - characterize the images of characters in short stories and poems. An in-depth psychological analysis of the experiences of S. Crane’s “little” hero is accompanied in his short stories by an appeal to the technique of internal monologue. S. Crane is deservedly considered today one of the first writers to use elements of the stream of consciousness technique.

With their help, the short stories highlight the paradox of a situation common in Crane's short stories, when the protagonist himself becomes a source of chaos. This technique maintains tense uncertainty, the effect of duality of what is happening, so characteristic of S. Crane’s artistic world.

In addition, as evidenced by many literary scholars, S. Crane’s merit is seen in the fact that he was one of the first to attempt to describe reality in terms of the well-known trinity: a lonely person, an indifferent universe and the feeling of confrontation that arises between them.

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